

"Inside the third space" podcast series

Insights from education design and development professionals

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The podcast series *Inside the Third Space* seeks to formalise and highlight the achievements of third space professionals, recognising their essential role in driving educational innovation and transformation across the higher education sector. While the series originates from the University of New South Wales, its insights are relevant to a broader community, acknowledging that third space professionals everywhere face similar challenges and opportunities.

The podcast series includes four episodes, each focusing on a different role within education design, development, and program teams, yielding valuable insights into the experiences, challenges, and transformative potential of third space professionals. A discussion forum is available for listeners to connect, share thoughts, and learn from each other's journeys.

Through this initiative, we invite engagement from the broader higher education community, creating an opportunity for dialogue, collaboration, and shared learning. By connecting with others in the field, we aim to inspire and empower professionals to navigate and leverage the "third space" in their own contexts, driving innovation and enhancing the overall educational experience across institutions.

For inquiries or to share your thoughts beyond the 3SS, feel free to reach us at insidethethirdspace@gmail.com

Inside the Third Space podcast

You can listen to the podcast right here in the Slowposium, or you can find it on [Spotify](#), [YouTube](#), [Apple Podcasts](#) or you can add [the RSS feed](#) to your favourite podcast platform.

Episode descriptions

Episode 1 – Lucy Jellema

https://open.spotify.com/embed/episode/2P7kKeYSROXBQRU922oYNY?utm_source=generator

Host Morgan Harris delves into the concept of the third space with Lucy Jellema, an Educational Developer for equity at UNSW Sydney. Lucy shares her journey, her role in supporting students from low socio-economic backgrounds, and insights into mental health among third-space professionals.

Episode 2 – Fiona Nicolson

https://open.spotify.com/embed/episode/62G7NN4BGjS2iHDqSfmsVK?utm_source=generator

Host Zara Khan explores the third space with Fiona Nicolson, manager of the Medicine and Health Education Development Unit at UNSW. Fiona shares her journey, insights into academic-professional collaboration, and the challenges and successes within this unique educational space.

Episode 3 – Natalie Gelche

https://open.spotify.com/embed/episode/1wGdEp8xpB8YfRrRBPkMeW?utm_source=generator

Host Nasrin Danish discusses the third space with Natalie Gelche, a Senior Educational Developer at UNSW. Natalie shares her journey from HR to the third space, navigating life as a non-academic in an academic world, and the significance of embracing AI in education.

Episode 4 – Samadhi Driscoll

https://open.spotify.com/embed/episode/0EaeOn9QSCOVPUqICy2AWh?utm_source=generator

Host Agneetha Amarnath dives into discussing the unique role of third-space professionals in higher education with guest Samadhi Driscoll, Nexus Program Lead at UNSW Sydney. Samadhi reveals how her background in education and psychology shapes her innovative approach to fostering collaboration and bridging academic and professional perspectives to create lasting impact.

About the authors

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Meredith was an Educational Developer in the Faculty of Arts, Design and Architecture, as part of the Nexus Program. With a Master's in TESOL, she has over twenty years of experience as an English language teacher, TESOL teacher trainer and materials and curriculum designer.

Ellie McDougall

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Ellie is an Educational Developer (Nexus) in the Faculty of Engineering with a background in science education.

Morgan Harris

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Swapneel holds a PhD in Engineering Education: within Nexus, he is an educational developer who currently leads the White Hat AI Hacking of Assessments project.

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